

Report on 2025

Greenland Marine Research Seminar *“Guiding the Course of Future Marine Research in Greenland”* & Workshop on Status and Development of East Greenland waters

November 11th, 2025
Hotel Hans Egede, Nuuk, Greenland

Nordic
Co-operation

GREENLAND
MARINE
RESEARCH
SEMINAR

Pinnngortitaleriffik
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of Natural Resources

AALBORG
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Authors: Rikke Becker Jacobsen, Thomas Juul-Pedersen and Søren Post

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With special workshop contributions and assistance from Qiteraġ Eugenius, AnnDorte Burmeister, Michael Sejr, Josefin Ekstedt, Furqan Asif and Konstantin Scherlund Houbak

Photographs: Christian Sølbeck

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2nd Biennial Greenland Marine Research Seminar “*Guiding the Course of Future Marine Research in Greenland*”

During Greenland Science Week 2025, the Greenlandic Institute of Natural Resources (GINR) and Greenland Climate Research Centre (GCRC) organized the 2nd Biennial Greenland Marine Research Seminar with financial support from Nordic Cooperation. Following from experiences and feed-back from the first seminar hosted in 2023¹, this seminar presented an opportunity to communicate not only research results and activities conducted by Greenlandic and international scientific institutions and programmes, but also to put a strong focus on communicating research and innovation activities conducted by other Greenlandic stakeholders and organisations. Registrations were received from 80 persons from 9 countries representing 41 organisations.

¹ Find information on the 1st Biennial Greenland Marine Research Seminar2023 in the seminar report: <https://zenodo.org/records/10977632>

Presentations

The seminar gathered participants from a range of scientific disciplines, research programmes, and stakeholder organisations, creating a setting for the presentation of ongoing work and diverse perspectives relevant to the seminar theme. During the seminar (hosted by Thomas Juul-Pedersen, GINR/GCRC), ten presentations covered a broad range of topics related to marine ecosystems and resources, and other maritime activities:

Marine research seen from a Greenlandic environmental organisation in dialogue with communities

Parnuna Egede Dahl - Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat

Linking the Greenland Ice Sheet to the Ocean: Dynamics from fjords to the coast

Lorenz Meire - Greenland Climate Research Centre/Greenland Institute of Natural Resources

Microscopic algae in focus: Connecting local and offshore processes to food webs

Tobias R. Vonnahme - Greenland Climate Research Centre/Greenland Institute of Natural Resources

Growing and zoning - regulating cruise tourism in Greenland

Carina Ren - Aalborg University

Arctic Council and biodiversity Monitoring, including the Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Programme...

Tom Christensen - Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Programme

Sea Urchins and sea cucumbers - trial fisheries in Greenland

Nikoline Ziemer - Royal Greenland

The Baffin Bay/Davis Strait Distributed Biological Observatory

Craig Lee - University of Washington

Towards an integrated view of marine phycotoxins in the Arctic region

Sofia Ribeiro - Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland

Building synergies around the 2026 CASCADES Expedition along the northwestern coast of Greenland

Jean-Éric Tremblay - Université Laval

Unravelling the “hidden” genetic diversity of Greenland’s marine ecosystems

Morten Tange Olsen - University of Copenhagen

Seminar Dialogue

The Seminar was conducted in a traditional conference style followed by a collective discussion of future marine research guided by 11 inspirational questions.

- How do you currently use marine research findings in your work or decision-making?
- What aspects of marine science or recent findings would you like to better understand?
- How can communication between marine scientists and stakeholders be improved?
- What marine changes or challenges are you most concerned about in Greenland's future?
- What partnerships or collaborations could strengthen marine research going forward?
- What formats or tools would help make marine research findings more accessible to you?
- What partnerships or collaborations could strengthen marine research going forward?
- How can we ensure marine research in Greenland benefits both science and society?
- How can marine research better integrate traditional or local knowledge?
- In what ways could marine research better support or inform your work or community needs?
- What key questions do you think future marine research in Greenland should aim to address?

The dialogue formed around two over-arching themes: reflections on ways to connect research with Greenlandic society, and the continued support of Greenlandic research institutions and international partnerships - also in new geopolitical contexts. Points made by participants are summarized based on recordings during the workshop. Anonymous quotations are included for further illustration of the points made.

An integrated summary of stakeholder ideas and suggestions from the marine seminar and the East Greenland waters workshop is available in the final chapter of this report (p. 30-31).

Connecting research with society

A fishery stakeholder opened the dialogue, raising the critique that many of the presentations lacked a **direct link to the commercial fisheries** that are — after all — at the very core to Greenland's economy and society. It was noted that the research community is still in the process of learning how to connect research to society and that the seminar is but one piece to this puzzle, and that participation and inclusion comes in many formats. Participants were thus encouraged to share further examples and ideas for how to connect research to society.

A researcher presented the key point that dialogue is something on-going, where relevance and mutual contributions are continuously explored and where time spent together builds trust.

“I think also getting to know ‘what can research do for industry and businesses’ and ‘what can businesses and industry do together with research’. It’s a really difficult question, working across disciplines, like how do we need each other how can we be relevant and meaningful to one another? And it is often really hard but I think that it is an ongoing thing, coming back and continuing the conversations. And trying to have these projects together. So there is not just one solution, but I feel that after 10 years, we know each other, we know what each other can do, and how we can collaborate. But it just, I mean I’m sorry to say, but time and building that trust and knowing each other, spending time together, that’s a part of one answer at least” (Researcher from Denmark)

That **time and presence build trust** was echoed in various comments across a diversity of research backgrounds:

“If you want to connect with community, spend time! Everybody is busy, but if you are serious about connecting, this is the only way” (Stakeholder from Qaanaaq).

“Reaching out to community might seem as an easy thing to do. But it is not. And over the past 20 years, research has changed. We have become more aware of how our findings are usable. Starts from the researcher, but also with the funders. Reaching out to industry was not a common thing 20 years ago(...) If you stay for a longer time, it becomes easier to connect” (Researcher from Greenland).

During the dialogue, the desirability of **establishing of various local hubs** - as a supplement to Arctic Hub in Nuuk - were expressed by a researcher from Norway:

“Most of us work at stations and vessels. So it is hard to integrate local knowledge and to invite into our venues, because it is seen as not theirs. And we don’t have long-term living (...) How do we maybe foster this sort of middle-ground between the scientists and the communities? What kind of institutions do we need to make that happen?” (Researcher from Norway)

A dialogue subsequently emerged about how **local concerns and observations speaks to the research presented** in the seminar regarding environmental changes and climate change:

“So, we have this narwhal here. A lot of scientists are saying that the numbers are decreasing. We think about this animal. Yes, there is hunting pressure that gets pressed by quota and a discussion between the scientist and the government (...) We know that the sea temperature is rising and changing the ecosystem, but we don’t know exactly how. There are some scientists out there trying to look at it. And then the sea ice is changing dramatically. What is it doing to the narwhal or what is it doing to the ecosystem? And it’s also changing the behavior of the hunters. So, there’s another thing. The algae thing was very interesting because I have heard some locals talking. We had no sea ice. It was all open sea for such a big area. And you know those things that stick to the bottom of the sea ice? It must have been different. Could it be that it affected that we don’t see narwhals anymore? It’s not just the sea ice, it’s the ecosystem. There are local people speculating about things like that. And then all the glaciers are climbing the mountains, we also know that. They climb it slowly, but the rich ecosystem in front of the tidewater glaciers, it’s changing and it’s going to change more. So, from the community perspective, there is this angry hunter. The government doesn’t give them quota. They see that the blubber of the narwhal, it used to be like this [stakeholder uses hands spread apart to indicate thickness]. I know it because I go hunting together. This autumn, it was like this [stakeholder uses hands to indicate thinner layer]. And there has been talk about that the animals are starving ‘I caught a beluga, but there was nothing to eat. Or, I heard a hunter caught a

walrus 'It was so thin. The stomach is empty. They're starving'. Also, we eat the contents of the stomach. The shells, the creatures inside the stomach, they're getting smaller too. They used to be this big, now they're like this [Indication of size, smaller]. The narwhal blubber has been visibly thinning during the past, I'm not sure, I've been hearing it for two, three years now. So, it might be going on for five years. My question here is, we have this animal here, and we have a community that is dependent on the animal very strongly. And there are so many things happening. And then the community thinks it's getting banged down the head. Only the hunting pressure is being taken care of. Okay, you can't change the climate in a few years. We all know that. But to justify their feelings, because the community has a regulation that is very sustainable about narwhals. [editor's note from stakeholder's previous comments: the region has had local regulations for decades that narwhal must be harvested the traditional and sustainable way by kayak and harpoon, for a silent hunt and to never lose prey once hit] But if it's going to change, because the glaciers, the tidewater glaciers are going to be gone for the grandchildren, what kind of conversation is needed? That's the thing that really occupies my mind a lot. Obviously, it is cross disciplinary, it's huge, it's massive" (Stakeholder from Qaanaq).

In cases where research and local communities wonder about similar processes and phenomena, connecting research to society may be a matter of **listening carefully to local questions** and exploring how existing research can be communicated and/or adapted to engage with local dialogues. This was summarized by a researcher from Greenland:

"So I think this is a very good example of how science also needs to listen more to the questions that are out there. It's not always easy to adapt your science entirely to questions that are out there, but very often you might be able to actually answer some of these questions without changing your whole way of working (Researcher from Greenland).

Sometimes, it is also a question of scientists describing the links, and perhaps also **communicating their motivations as scientists** as part of their communication. This was expressed by a researcher from Greenland:

"Many questions that you might be faced, that we also hear now, how is this climate change affecting the now also in North West Greenland for instance, or other questions that are very much on people's mind. You might have to start somewhere else to address this, and then it's not always easy to see the link between the work you do. So to understand what happens to the now, you might have to start at what happens to the glaciers, what happens to the fjord ecosystem, what happens to the phytoplankton, what happens to ocean acidification, these things that feeds up through the system. But as scientists in general, I think, we have not always been very good at communicating this link. Why is it that I'm doing this? Because one thing I think we can say, as being a scientist myself, is that a lot of what we do is based on our personal commitment to this. We are not doing this just for the sake of money. We all started out as scientists because we want to change things, we want to understand things, we want to make a difference. Making that difference and connecting that link is super important to communicate as well. And that is sometimes lost or not done as well as it could be. But I think it's something we are slowly getting better at" (Researcher from Greenland)

When working directly and closely with communities, **research questions should, when relevant and possible, be re-formulated to respond to local interests and needs.** A Canadian researcher shared her own learning as an example:

“A quick story, when I was a master’s student. I was sent to [do] a community work in Nunavut and with a research question which was very broad. It was around mining, and I even forget the question actually. I thought, to tell you the truth, it [the question] was very like in the cloud. And when I arrived at the community, I was there for three months, and the women that I interviewed were like, ‘honey, you’re sweet, but your question we don’t care’[about it] (...) And so we sit down, and we actually co-created the question and it was around how the community could benefit from the mining. So it was kind of helping my master’s degree because it was still around mining, but then the question was, ‘what is a happy community? What do we need to be happy?’ And list, actually a list of things they need, and then we asked the company to finance those activities” (Researcher from Canada).

Another researcher reflected on the experience that not all interesting research questions (in this case on algae bloom) were considered relevant for the industry, by the industry. In such situations, it was argued, research questions should not be forced upon stakeholders. Instead, outreach and relevance could be secured in cooperation with other groups, e.g. through **general education**.

“Be aware of what you don’t want to do. For example there are a lot of ideas regarding algae bloom - but not all is relevant to community. Algae bloom can be harmful, but it is not an imminent threat to industry. So we engaged with education rather than industry. We did not want to force a topic on to stakeholders (...) If I talk to industry and they do not see a threat - then I think it is okay to step away and focus on education instead” (researcher).

A final point of dialogue was presented from a management perspective, highlighting the importance of communicating research to the **Greenlandic public**: *“As a good example I want to highlight Greenland Institute of Natural Resources. They do good work to communicate their projects on social media and KNR [Greenland national broadcasting]” (stakeholder from Greenland).*

Ensuring marine research in a new geopolitical context

A question was initially raised about the connection between research and **geopolitical development**, as one researcher expressed concerns for deterioration of funding, loss of research positions in certain countries and investment priorities towards defense in other regions. How can marine research in the Arctic be ensured in the future? Towards the end of the seminar dialogues about science communication and societal connection returned back to the changing geopolitical context - emphasizing the need to keep going.

Nationally, **scientific institutions continue despite setbacks and changes in the geopolitical situation**. Greenlandic researchers discussed that Greenlandic research institutions and Arctic Hub try to do as much as possible with the resources they have in terms of connecting with society. **Continued international cooperation remains important for local community connections**, a Greenlandic researcher explained: *“the more we collaborate with [local] people from our institute, the more capacity we also build up here. And the better we become at actually linking out and saying, you know what, if you want to do work up here, go and talk to this person. Or why not hold a meeting up here where we talk about this issue, or a workshop where we go in and try and address this”* (researcher from Greenland).

Greenlandic researchers also consider it important to strengthen the Greenlandic research institutions and Arctic Hub.

The discussion subsequently segued into a discussion among Greenlandic and international scientists about the importance of data sharing – including **data standardization and shared databases**, highlighting the inclusion of Greenland as well as the role of international partnerships in taking on such standardization and sharing tasks. Discussions eventually touched upon the sheer number of surveys received by Greenlandic authorities each year, and the need to ensure that **research activities are communicated and connected rather than duplicated**, and that important gaps are actually covered. A manager explained: *“I think it's extremely important to have the local connection, but also the connection in the scientific community, because that way we ensure that all the knowledge comes back to the people who need it to work and to make decisions, but also that we don't have any missing steps or duplicating projects or data”* (Greenlandic stakeholder).

List of registered participants for the Greenland Marine Research Seminar 2025

Aalborg University
Aarhus University
Amundsen Science
Arctic Command
Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Programme (CBMP)
Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF)
Dalhousie University
Danish Meteorological Institute
DataONE & Arctic Data Center
Fishermen and Hunters Association in Greenland (KNAPK)
Foundation Tara Océan
French Embassy
Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland
Greenland Business Association
Greenland Climate Research Centre
Greenland Institute of Natural Resources
Harvard University
ILLU Ilulissat
Kommuneqarfik Sermersooq (Sermersooq Municipality)
Leipzig University

Ministry for Nature and Environment
Ministry of Fisheries, Hunting, Agriculture and Self-sufficiency (APNIPN)
Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat
Qalerualinniat Aalisagarniallu Kattuffiat (QAK)
Royal Greenland
Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey
Sigguk A/S
Students on Ice Foundation
Swiss Polar Institute
Technical University of Denmark
The Arctic University of Norway
Ultima Thule
Université du Québec à Rimouski
Université Laval
University of Alberta
University of Bergen
University of Colorado Boulder
University of Copenhagen
University of Oldenburg
University of Washington
Utrecht University

Workshop on Status and Development of East Greenland Waters

Under the initiative of the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) Working Group on Integrated Ecosystem Assessment of the Greenland Sea (WGIEAGS), and with financial support from Nordic Co-operation, a 2nd stakeholder workshop was organized. The workshop brought together stakeholders in sharing knowledge and perspectives on the sustainable development and usage of the East Greenlandic ecosystem. The workshop followed a previous workshop held in 2023², focusing on four thematic areas of stakeholder cooperation in an ecosystem-based management context. The workshop was attended by 35 people from 20 organisations.

² Find information on the 1st Workshop on Status and Development of East Greenlandic waters 2023 in the seminar report: <https://zenodo.org/records/10977632>

The workshop opened with a short introduction to the on-going work of the WGIEAGS working group (Søren Post, GINR); an overview of oceanic trends in the East Greenland Ecoregion (Colin Stedmon, DTU); a status on the coastal development plan for coastal fisheries in East Greenland (Rebekka Nygaard Bak, APNIPN); and a re-cap of stakeholder input from the WGIEAGS working group (Rikke Jacobsen, AAU) followed by an introduction to the workshop format of the day. This reporting of stakeholder inputs is summarized and translated into English by the authors. Direct quotations are based on recordings during the workshop and presented in the original languages of the working groups: either in English, Danish or Danish in-situ translations from Greenlandic.

A changing ocean with shifting fishing grounds

The scientific presentation of the overall oceanic trends in the eco-region presented results from a recent article by Gjelstrup et al. 2025³. It was explained how the ‘fronts’ between different water masses are characterized by high ecological productivity, sustaining fisheries around the globe. In East Greenland the front between the colder, less saline Polar water and the warmer, more saline Atlantic water is responding to the wind system of the Sub-polar gyre; periods with weakening of this wind system correlate with weaker ecological productivity observed as a decrease in algae growth. The position of the front is dynamic, sometimes moving closer to Greenland (some 150 km closer to Ammassalik). But whereas the fronts movement followed the seasons back in the 1990s, the front has moved closer to Greenland on a more permanent basis. From a fishery perspective it was hypothetically suggested that current ocean dynamics is likely to cause 1) productive fishing grounds to shift locations 2) a shift in species composition from Arctic to Atlantic species.

³ Gjelstrup, C. V. B., Boje, J., MacKenzie, B. R., Post, S., Werner, K. M., Visser, A. W., & Stedmon, C. A. (2025). The East Greenland Polar Front as a mediator of climate-ocean-ecosystem variability along southeast Greenland. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 130(10). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2025JC022669>

Frontens intensitet og variabilitet i subpolare gyre

Note: SPG inverted

- Vedvarende perioder med høj (stærk) og lav (svag) front
- Skift korrelerer med SPG-indeks

St...
Re...
polare Nordatlanten
fra subpolare og

Interestingly, a stakeholder from the offshore fishing fleet had provided observations prior to the workshop that also spoke to the notion of fishing grounds as dynamically shifting – in this instance the fishery for Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*) on the East Coast. It was explained how the cod is ‘constantly moving’ and how their offshore trawler must constantly change positions as well. In a governance context, this translates into a call for greater flexibility by expanding the fishing season and the permit area for cod fishing – while respecting spawning periods (see box 1).

BOX 1:

“[navn på fartøj] fisker pt. ved Kap Farvel på vestsiden, der kan I se på tracking [kort vedhæftet], at de er nødt til at flytte sig hele tiden, da torsken flytter sig konstant. Det er lokalt bevis på at torsken flytter sig konstant. I sidste ende er det de samme torske i øst vi fisker i øst i de 2 områder som vedlagte skitse viser. Vi lærer noget nyt hele tiden, og i forbindelse med læring flytter argumenterne også hele tiden. Derfor er det nødvendigt relativt fleksibel forvaltningsplan. [Der er følgende] argumenter, set fra [navn på fartøj] side som kun har en licens til at fiske kun Dohrn Banken, [for at] øst området bliver til et område (...):

- Fiskeriet bliver generelt mere fleksibelt
- Fiske tidspunktet vil kunne være året rundt, og ikke kun i november, december, maj og juni.
- Fiskeri trykket vil sprede til hele østkysten for hele året.
- Og vores nationale fiskeri vil ikke være i konflikt med dem vi har bilaterale aftaler med, da de også er velkomne, til at fiske i hele østkysten. De har jo i princippet også begrænset kvoter.
- På den måde lærer vi også løbende hele østkystens fiskeri muligheder.
- Men stadigvæk med respekt for de eksisterende gyde områder og tidspunkter”

(Stakeholder input, provided prior to workshop)

Following the introductory presentations at the workshop, participations were grouped into four thematic working groups with different sets of dialogue questions. Participants had been grouped according to their professional background and expertise. Themes, questions and background are listed below and workshop discussions are summarized based on written notes and audio recordings in the subsequent section. Dialogues were conducted in Danish and Greenlandic, but have been summarized in English for this report. Quotes in presenters language (Danish) are included throughout for specific details on the original wordings and concepts used.

Workshop theme & questions	Participants
<u>A changing ecosystem</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can we adapt fishing, hunting and nature-use to a changing ecosystem? • What changes in nature do you see/foresee in your work? • Are there tendencies that makes hunting and fishery more difficult or easier? • What is important to protect or preserve in the area - and why? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Royal Greenland • Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (GINR) • Fisher/hunter from Tasiilaq • Fisher/hunter from Kuumiut • Ministry of fishing, hunting, agriculture and Self-sufficiency (APNIPN) • Student from SILA education
<u>Sustainable use and balance</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do we find the balance between use and protection of the nature? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greenlandic Employers • Ministry of fishing, hunting, agriculture and self-sufficiency (APNIPN)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What does 'sustainable use' mean to you in practice? • Are there places, periods or species where there are needs for special consideration? • How can practices, rules or cooperation be adapted to ensure sustainability and co-existence of activities? • How do you experience that national and international rules and agreements (e.g. around ocean protection, fishing & hunting, tourism) affect the possibilities of conducting a sustainable business? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The environmental agency for mineral resource activities (EAMRA) • Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF) • Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat • Greenlandic Institute of Natural Resources • Aarhus University • Aalborg University
<p><u>Cooperation and knowledgesharing</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can scientists, managers and local communities better cooperate around monitoring and decision-making? • How can local knowledge and research results best be combined in management? • What makes cooperation possible - and what makes it difficult today? • What considerations should one take as researcher and manager from 'outside'? • How can results and experiences from research and management be better communicated back to local communities? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qalerualinniat Aalisagarniallu Kattuffiat (QAK) • Sikuaq trawl & Niisa Trawl • Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat • Greenland Institute of Natural Resources • Aalborg University
<p><u>Future and decision-making</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can local voices get more influence on how the area is used and regulated in the future? • What knowledge and documentation is often lacking when decisions are made? • What can be done in order for management to more actively use observations from locals and the industry? • How can/should local knowledge and perspectives be included in management? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of fishing, hunting, agriculture and self-sufficiency (APNIPN) • Royal Greenland Fish factory management, Tasiilaq • The environmental agency for mineral resource activities (EAMRA) • Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat • Technical University of Denmark • Aalborg University

A changing ecosystem

This first workshop group discussed the theme of a changing ecosystem and managed to talk about three questions. The first question was how to adapt fishery, hunting and use of nature to a changing ecosystem, which was considered a comprehensive question - “how do you adapt to that?”. Some of what was heard during the discussions was that adaptations to change is something that has always occurred, but one thing is adaptation to one parameter. Another thing is **when a lot of parameters are changing at once:**

”Specielt hvis det er én ændring i isen eller vindforholdet. Men når alle de her ting ændrer sig på samme tid, så er det rigtig svært at tilpasse. Så det er mere et spørgsmål om det her med, hvor kraftigt og hvor mange parametre, der ændrer sig på en gang. Og det gør det rigtig svært at tilpasse sig. Og noget af det vi hørte, det var, at... Der er perioder nu, hvor det kan være virkelig svært at opretholde en normal fiskeri og fangst. Fordi forandringerne sker så kraftigt og så mange ting på én gang. Og det er både is og det er vind og også strømforhold, som vi også har hørt om”
(Presenter summarizing group 1 discussion)

Hunters explained that the changing presences of animals make it difficult to uphold the everyday economy as nature plays a huge role in sustaining daily life. Hunters adapt naturally to nature and its way of changing. But the longer duration of storms present a challenge. Reflections on hunters’ resilience focused on the need for adapting target species and hunting equipment. The drift ice passing around Tasiilaq arrives later and it facilitates hunting beyond the usual season and into October-November. Also, the changes are bringing more fish to the area, providing new opportunities for income.

The **targeting of new species** was identified as a key adaptation action in East Greenland such as targeting smaller whales now that hunters are catching fewer seals. It was also discussed that these new hunting practices could benefit from more knowledge sharing - e.g. with the Faroese Islands who have traditionally hunted the smaller whales:

”En anden ting vi også snakkede om, det var, at den måde man kan tilpasse sig på, det er blandt andet det her med, som man også begynder at se på Østkysten, at man måske jager nye arter. Så småhvaler er måske blevet en større del af den fangst, man har derovre, end det har været tidligere. Det der så er en udfordring her, eller kan være en udfordring, er, at man måske ikke har den samme erfaring i at jage og udnytte de her hvaler. Og der snakkede vi noget om, at der var f.eks. eksempler på, hvordan at hvis man havde mere traditionelle jagtmetoder med harpun, så har man større succesrate, end hvis man skyder den med rifler, hvor der er en større tendens til, at dyrene synker. Og det er sådan en udfordring, som er lidt svær at håndtere, hvor noget af det, som blev foreslået her, det var, at man kunne godt lave en vidensudveksling, f.eks. med Færøerne, som har stor erfaring med småhvalsjagt” (Presenter summarizing group 1 discussion)

Hunters have tried to drive the smaller whale ashore once, but most typically they hunt them with harpoons. It was told that especially the younger generation of hunters have been observed to shoot

the animals - both dolphins, pilot whales and orcas - before using the harpoon, which has resulted in wounded animals. And thus, there were reflections around the need for younger hunters to perhaps change their hunting methods. In Nunavik hunting methods have been adapted to the new species coming from south, and hunters from Tasiilaq see a potential in learning from the Faroese Islands in relation to Pilot whale hunting.

Adaptation of management is further challenged by the fact that **both fleets and target species are constantly adapting to environmental changes**. The offshore fishery has observed a lot of cod in East Greenland and catches have increased and the industry has advised an increase of quota. Meanwhile cod and catches close to the shore are observed to fluctuate as when for example 2024 catches were smaller due to a prolonged period of sea ice, which shortened the fishing season and then the industry observes the well-known 'rule of thumb: 'When cod goes up in the Barent sea, it goes down in Greenland'. It was discussed how the industry would typically observe changes in 'real-time; how science have difficulties assessing conditions and trends with certainty; and how management - as result - tends to respond with delay. The need for closer communication between fishers and science was therefore highlighted.

"I industrien bliver der også snakket meget om at der er et meget stort torskefiske ved Østgrønland i nogle områder har det virkelig godt gået op. Men det er meget sådan i perioder, og det vil sige, at en af de måder, man tilpasser måske fiskeriet på, det er, at man bliver mere fokuseret på at gå efter torsken i bestemte perioder, og målrette fiskeriet i de perioder og i de områder, hvor man ved, at torsken er. Og igen, så kan sådan noget som storisen også være en god udfordring for det. Men igen, så er der muligvis også en sammenhæng til andre områder, som du har sagt, så var der måske sådan en tommelfingerregel, man havde omkring, at når tingene ser ud til at gå opad i Barentshavet, så går det nedad herovre, modsat f.eks. med torsken. Og det er jo måske noget, hvor vi ikke har den store viden omkring det, og det kom vi også ind på, at den måde tingene ofte foregår på, så er det dem, som ligesom er ude og fiske og fange, som ser tingene først. Og så er det først, hvis det er noget, der foregår en længere periode, så begynder forskningen ligesom at komme efter og forstå det her, og så først derefter bliver det implementeret ind i forvaltningen. Så der er sådan en forsinkelse i den her proces her også, hvor den her kommunikation direkte imellem f.eks. fisker og fangere og forskerne, at der vil man kunne speede tingene op og måske målrette tingene lidt mere også" (Presenter summarizing working group 1 discussion)

As an example of close communication scientists highlighted the communication between land- and seabased observations e.g. when incidents of heavy rain have occurred, which may cause strong run-offs into the fiords.

Another idea for research included an investigation into different types of cod as the fishers seem to have observed three different types of cod, namely one that has a darker colour and smaller; and some at that are lighter; and then there are some that are thinner.

The **impacts on ringed seal** due to glacier retreats and fiord systems opening up was discussed with reference to comparative observations of Ilulissat fiord and Semilik fiord. It was suggested that there should perhaps be put a limit on how far into the fiord seal hunting should be allowed. A hunter expressed that he did not think they would catch all seals because seals adapt to changing

ocean currents (strømforhold), which in turns limits the hunter. In Ilulissat however, a lot of seals are now being caught after the main fiord has opened up, allowing hunters access to catch more seals in other parts of the fiord. The point was then raised that seals breed in very large areas and oftentimes it is not possible to reach the seals. It was noted that there is insufficient knowledge about the hunting in Sermilik due to a lack of reporting of the catches and scientists have put transmitters on seals in the Sermilik fiord to follow the development now that the fiord has opened up. There are concerns that increased marine traffic scares off the animals, but 28 of the 30 seals with transmitters have stayed in the Sermilik fiord. Hunters furthermore think that the whales are contributing to the decline of seal, and both hunters and scientists agree that there are a lot of whales offshore in east Greenland. A hunter suggested that larger seals should perhaps be protected altogether (fredes) or caught to a lesser extent because they are the animals that breed.

Hunters were asked about the presence of **Polar cod (*Boreagadus saida*)** and hunters informed that they are present in different areas, but that they are generally catching less.

The industry informed that they often discover different species when the research ships are not there, and it encourages the scientific research vessel (Tarajoq) to come to East Greenland and **do research outside of the season.**

The industry also notes that the shrimp fishery is peculiar in the sense that they experience very good shrimp fisheries on 'Dohrn banke', catching large shrimps only. During an experimental fishery in northeast Greenland, they experienced that the water intake was blocked by shrimps. In general there is too little knowledge about shrimps in East Greenland. GINR expressed a wish for shared briefings if and when the industry observes something on a recurring basis.

Sustainable use and balance

The second workshop group discussed **the notion of sustainability** and what that might entail in practice, in the context of the East Greenlandic ecosystem. The diverse composition of the group (including managers, industry and scientists) meant that various different perspectives on sustainability had been raised, and as the rapporteur of the discussion summarized it, it was important to have all perspectives presented around the table. He also suggested that shared commonality across perspectives was suggested: that the effect of sustainability may simply be to maximize the value in a broad sense from the living resource with the common good at the centre.

“ Ja, vores emne var bæredygtighed, og hvad det var i praksis. Og jeg tror, det var meget interessant. Altså, vi var meget forskellige. Der var både forskere og folk fra management og fra erhvervet. Og jeg tror, vi blev enige om, at bæredygtighed kan være ret forskelligt. Det var enormt vigtigt, at vi fik alle synspunkter på bordet om, hvad bæredygtighed var, og hvordan man implementerede det. Men jeg tror også, der var enighed om, at... At effekten af bæredygtighed, det er måske bare, at man maksimerer værdien i bred forstand på en eller anden levende ressource. Så alle var jo sådan set interesserede i at stille mod bæredygtighed, fordi det var til fælles bedste”. (Presenter summarizing group 2 discussion)

Regional differences were discussed, highlighting how the local population plays an important role in sustainability discussions around quotas and tourism pressures in the South. Meanwhile, the north does not have the same degree of local and public attention to for example, tourism impacts, constituting a sort of awareness and information gap in relation to governance:

”Så havde vi en del snak omkring den her store forskel der i Østgrønland på den sydlige del, hvor vi har sådan en mere intensiveret fangst og fiskeri, hvor der selvfølgelig var mere behov for måske kvoter og kig på bæredygtighed i klassisk forstand. Og så har vi det nordlige, hvor presset måske mest er fra turisme, og hvor man kan sige, der ikke er den helt store lokalbefolkning til at...måske række fingrene op og sige, ’nu er det for meget’, eller ’nu er det for lidt’. Så der er måske et behov for, at man har lidt fokus på Nationalparken og det nordlige Grønland og prøve at finde ud af, hvad der egentlig foregår der. Fordi der er... Der er ikke ret mange mennesker til at holde øje med det. Så det er meget vigtigt at finde ud af, hvad der sker deroppe”. (Presenter summarizing working group 2 discussion)

Having Greenlandic fish quota fished and landed in and by Greenland was also explored from a sustainability perspective, insofar that shorter transport distance and more efficient fishing trips could lower the **carbon footprint** of the fishery.

“Og der var sådan en snak omkring det her med, at der ville være mange gode argumenter for, at fodprintet, eller både sådan i form af CO2 og bæredygtighed, der var meget vundet ved, at fiskeriet forblev i Grønland. Altså den... Den ekspertise, der findes, kunne man godt argumentere for, at det betød, at der måske var en mere effektiv fiskeri. Og der er ingen tvivl om, at kvoter og skibene skal sejle ud for at fiske og kan indhandle tingene. Det giver da et mindre footprint. Så der var sådan en snak om, om man kunne finde nogle gode argumenter, som i bredere forstand på, at det her med at holde fiskeriet på grønlandske hænder, måske kunne være interessant. Men er vi jo også enige om, at interessen sydfra, den er nok ikke mindskes i fremtiden” (Presenter summarizing working group 2 discussion)

Cooperation and knowledge sharing

The third workshop group had broad dialogues around cooperation and knowledge sharing between local communities, scientists and management. The group agreed that there is a need for better dialogues between biologists, managers and the industry to stay up to date on the status for different species; it is important for everyone to have the newest available knowledge about the conditions of stocks and scientific advice. **Proximity** emerged as an important factor here: *“the closer we are to each other, the more dialogue we have, and the more knowledge we have about the resources”* (Presenter summarizing working group 3 discussion).

Sometimes there is limited scientific knowledge about certain species due to limited scientific resources and capacity. In such instances, more information could be obtained through scientific cooperation with fishers and hunters. The (Danish) concept of ‘**nøglefiskere**’ or ‘**nøgleflåder**’ (‘key-fishers and ‘key-fleets’) was put forward as a possible model for cooperation - that is designated fishers who can assist with monitoring through samplings etc. To establish and run such programmes, mutual trust and reliability need to be carefully considered and built-up:

”Der er situationer, hvor vi ikke foretager undersøgelser, på grund af, at det har vi ikke kapacitet til. Men hvis man så ønsker at have noget mere information om den her ressource, hvordan kan det så sikres i samarbejde med fiskerne eller fangerne. Og det kunne være, at man ligesom havde nogle nøglepersoner i nøgleflåden, som kunne være med til at lave nogle biologiske undersøgelser. For eksempel gå ud og sætte nogle garn et bestemt sted, på et bestemt tidspunkt. For at få en oplysning om, det kunne være stenbidere eller en anden fiskeart, eller krabber. Det kunne være en måde, man kunne gøre det på, og det ved vi godt er rigtig svært. Vi anerkender, at det kan være svært. Så hvordan er det, man får en indledende dialog med fiskerne og fangerne omkring, og laver sådan et overvågningsprogram sammen. Hvordan får vi en fælles dialog, en fælles forståelse for, at hvis fisker og fanger ønsker at indgå i sådan et samarbejde, så skal man ligesom have en

stolthedskultur, som gør, 'okay, jeg er virkelig med til at have viden omkring en ressource i et lokalområde'. Ja, det havde vi mange forskellige drøftelser omkring, og kunne være rigtig interessant at se mere på det, og arbejde hen imod det fremadrettet. Men igen, så er det sådan noget med, at vi skal have tillid til hinanden, så man ved, at hvis man som fisker og fanger laver de her undersøgelser for Naturinstituttets forskere, hvordan er det så, det bliver brugt, og kan man stole på hinanden" (Presenter summarizing working group 3 discussion).

The question of how best to combine local knowledge and research results in management sparked a discussion for the need to **clarify the understanding and expectations towards local knowledge**, and to have a clear plan for how to use it:

"Så havde vi et spørgsmål omkring, hvordan kan lokalviden og forskningsresultater bedst kombineres i forvaltningen. Det havde vi også en lang diskussion omkring, men også i forhold til, sådan helt basalt, hvad er det vi mener, når vi taler om lokalviden. Hvad er det, man ønsker af lokalviden, og hvordan er det så, man ønsker, den skal anvendes i forbindelse med forvaltningen. Så her, det vi ville foreslå, det var altså ligesom at få defineret, jamen hvilke oplysninger er det, vi ønsker, for at man kan sige, det her er en lokalviden. Og så også nogle helt klare tanker for, hvordan det skal implementeres i forvaltningen" (Presenter summarizing working group 3 discussion).

The condition of stocks is likely to impact knowledge cooperation and it was suggested that **different 'phases' provide different challenges and opportunities**. Cooperation is likely to be more easy when stocks are assessed by all to be in a very positive or in a very critical condition. Cooperation is typically more tricky in phases where early signs of stock decrease begin to show, as hunters and scientists tend to disagree on the relevant actions:

"Så var der sådan noget omkring, hvad gør samarbejdet nemt, og hvad gør det svært. (...) i de her situationer, hvor vi har en god bestand, hvor der er masser at fiske på eller fangst på, så er det altså meget nemmere at komme og samarbejde om nogle ting, eller have en dialog. Hvorimod i de perioder, hvor en bestand er for nedadgående, eller det bliver færre, så er det jo lidt mere, at det bliver færre fangstyr, så begynder man som forsker, biologer, fisker/fanger måske at blive uenige, og hvordan er det så, man takler den situation. Så bringer bestanden sig ned på et lavt niveau, hvor fisker/fangerne måske begynder at udtrykke bekymring om, at nu er vi på et lavt niveau, så er uenigheden måske ikke så stor" (Presenter summarizing working group 3 discussion).

Early information and **equitable dialogue** — *møde folk i øjenhøjde* - was identified as important considerations when building knowledge cooperation with local communities. Informing local communities about upcoming research projects is essential. And discussing new monitoring and survey programmes with hunters and fishers will allow for their expertise to inform the where and when of the research design (location of stations, time of samplings):

"Så var der det der med, 'hvilke hensyn til lokalbefolkningen bør forskere og forvaltere udfra tage?' Og det kunne være i forbindelse med noget, hvis man skal ind og implementere et forskningsprojekt, eller lave nye undersøgelser, så er det, at man tager kontakt til lokalbefolkningen, og informerer omkring, hvad er det for en undersøgelse, man skal lave. Det kunne også være, hvis nu man skulle iværksætte et nyt survey, et monteringsprogram, at man

tager henvendelse til de lokale fiskere og fangere, og siger, 'I har kendskab til det her område, hvor mener I, vi skal lægge nogle stationer?' Men igen, møder folk i øjenhøjde, fordi det også giver tillid, og også er en værdig måde at kommunikere på, begge veje rundt" (Presenter summarizing working group 3 discussion).

Future and decisions

The fourth workshop group discussed future decision-making and local inclusion in the governance of the East Greenlandic ecosystem. How to increase the influence of local voices was first discussed and some concrete opportunities were highlighted.

Firstly, **the special situation of the East Greenlandic fisheries makes the contribution of local knowledge and cooperation especially relevant.** Fisheries in East Greenland - especially coastal fisheries - are expanding from a low level compared to the fisheries on the West Coast. Scientific fishery surveys are sparse and local knowledge can help cover knowledge gaps historically and at present, and local fishers may contribute with **monitoring and sampling** activities.

A scientist noted that GINR has conducted several experimental surveys with limited success in identifying substantial fish concentrations. It was argued that involving fishers directly in exploratory fishing may yield more useful results, not only because fishers actively assess whether a resource is economically viable, but also because they may be able to monitor and search for commercially relevant stocks more cost-effectively than research vessels in this region.

As another example of cooperation, an example from Ummaanq was presented where a fisher has agreed to lower a CTD in between his own fishing hauls. The point was made that insofar that fishers assistance with samplings and monitoring takes off, it would be ideal to organize it so that the fishers themselves also have an interest in the specific measurements; that the data has some degree of relevance to his/her needs; and that the analytical results are communicated back to the fisher. It has been noted by the environmental NGO Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat that fishers already have a focus on stomach content and the conditions of the animal e.g. their fat layers.

Additional ideas for fisher/science cooperation emerged from the dialogue, including the idea of **integrating it with local school teaching.** Classroom teaching could have children in analyzing the local samples taken by local fishers (e.g. fishers they know) as a way to learn about science and knowledge cooperation with a basis in their immediate marine environment. Visiting scientists could assist with hands-on exercises, and/or instruction videos in local language could be developed to guide classroom activities with the local teacher. Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat has had experience with the latter on a project where children assisted with ice sampling (developing the video included observing and talking to the the children about how they followed the instructions, and included re-writing and adaptation of the instructions until the children managed to do the task correctly)

The working group discussed the **conditions and opportunities for establishing local dialogues in East Greenland.** Experiences from including fisher perspectives into the Greenlandic Government's

recent fishery development plan⁴ highlighted the critical issue of unstable telecommunications infrastructure and the value of going to East Greenland in person (seminars were organised with duration of 2-3 days with compensation for fishers transport, accommodation and lost work time). **Personal communication over telephone** to individual fishers was highly valuable and productive, but the communication model is also vulnerable in the sense that dialogue relies on one key person in the Government (APNIPN) administration. Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat shared their perspectives on how engagement could be strengthened by **combining multiple formats and following local advice**. Possible methods include listening tours to the location; sharing public information/press release with invitations to dialogue prior to arrival; and arranging longer sailing trips together. APNIPN also has experience with distributing surveys.

A second concrete suggestion for enhancing local voices in management was to have **East Greenland representation in the East Greenland working group of the fishery council**. Currently there is no representation and it would be good to have a person from East Greenland in the group, who can participate for an *extended* period of time. A third opportunity identified was the new tourism law which has now opened up a new window of opportunity for local influence in area-based ecosystem governance. With the **new tourism law** Greenlandic municipalities have now been given the mandate to explore and implement ‘zoning’ of human activities etc.

Co-management arrangements in the new coastal fisheries was discussed. The special situation in East Greenland – with fisheries starting almost from scratch – could be an **opportunity to experiment with other modes of fishery governance** than what is done (with varying success) on the West Coast. The advantage in East Greenland right now is that the coastal fishery management is focused on developing the coastal fishery and there are no immediate disagreements over the state of fish resources and managing the overall fishing pressure here and now is not in focus. This situation may also imply an opportunity to focus in on more/other relevant ecosystem aspects.

The extent to which **small vessel traffic** in East Greenland may impact fisheries was raised as a question by a stakeholder from Tasiilaq. Scientists suggested that pelagic species may react to marine traffic, but it would also depend on the frequency of the traffic; whether it is single passage or a steady schedule.

Another local question focused on the possible prospects of **local employment on offshore trawlers** operating on the East Coast. APNIN informed that many factors have to be in place for landing larger vessels; airport, bunker facilities and crew in place.

Education and training of East Greenlandic fishers was suggested, and a stakeholder informed that the municipality is in the process of establishing a new fishery school. Inviting a fisher over from West Greenland to teach was put forward as a suggestion (In fact, fishers have previously expressed interest in learning from West Greenlandic fishers and at the APNIN seminar a fisher selected by KNAPK came over to present the principles of gillnet fishing).

⁴https://naalakkersuisut.gl/-/media/horinger/2023/10/1310_udviklingsplan/udviklingsplan-for-fiskeriet-i-stgrnland-2023-2030-da.pdf

In light of the many concrete ideas emerging from the group, it was suggested to develop a **shared project catalogue** that could be used for future fundraising/applications. APNIN noted that the fishery development plan includes a budget for development projects, and it was discussed that this could perhaps be used as **co-funding** for larger applications.

Future formats for ecosystem dialogues

Rounding up the seminar on East Greenland, the organiser highlighted the wish for maintaining an on-going dialogue around the East Greenlandic ecosystem and its governance. Participants were encouraged to provide their inputs and share ideas and wishes for future dialogue formats.

APNIPN suggested that the seminar is hosted in East Greenland next time. This possibility was explored further, noting that it would likely mean better representation of local community, but also fewer researchers and that it would require much more funding.

The possibility of other institutions and organisations co-organising the format and content of the seminar was also opened up.

The relevance of organising similar seminars for West Greenlandic areas was also mentioned in recognition of the fact, that many of the questions debated here holds relevance for all of Greenland.

Finally, shared projects (and project applications) was highlighted as a potential avenue for continuing the cooperation around East Greenland

List of registered participants on Status and Development of East Greenland Waters 2025

Aalborg University
Aarhus University
Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF)
Fisher/hunter from Tasiilaq
Fisher/hunter from Kuumiut
Chairman of Tasiilaq branch of KNAPK
Greenland Business Association
Greenland Climate Research Centre
Greenland Institute of Natural Resources
Sermersooq Municipality
Ministry for Nature and Environment
Ministry of Fisheries, Hunting, Agriculture and Self-sufficiency (APNIPN)
Oceans North Kalaallit Nunaat
Polar Seafood
Qalerualinniat Aalisagarniallu Kattuffiat (QAK)
Royal Greenland
Sikuaq trawl / Niisa Trawl
Student from SILA education in Nuuk
Technical University of Denmark
The environmental agency for mineral resource activities (EAMRA)

Summary of seminar and workshop ideas & suggestions

Researcher/community cooperation

- Spend time with local communities and a broad range of stakeholders to build trust
- Use multiple formats to build local dialogues
- Engage in early and equitable forms of dialogues about the planned research
- Listen carefully to local questions - can they be answered with existing research and or by re-formulating your research questions?
- Not all research questions are matched by an interest from a concrete stakeholder - but they may be relevant for the public and/or educational purposes
- Facilitate continued contact between researchers and stakeholders to identify shared research interests
- When reaching out and coordinating with Greenlandic research institutions (Arctic Hub, GINR etc.), international research can help expand and build Greenlandic capacity for community-science cooperation
- Establish locally owned/managed research hubs in more Greenlandic communities
- Use the many knowledge gaps around the fish resources in East Greenland to develop ways of including local knowledge and local cooperation
- As scientists and fishers work together, consider cooperation with local education (children and youth)

Research coordination:

- Overview and coordination should ensure that research in Greenland is not duplicated - and that research gaps are identified and covered.
- Data from and about Greenland should be shared with Greenland
- Scientists and industry should keep each other informed about their real-time observation of changes and possible tendencies and thereby seek to minimize 'delays' in scientific conclusions and management action
- More scientific research on East Greenlandic resources (industry has noted high abundance of shrimps on Dohrn Banke; and that new species are often observed outside of the scientific survey season)
- Consider risks and hurdles for science/fisher cooperation: Disagreement may be lowest when stocks are in good – or in very critical – conditions. Disagreement may be at its highest when stock conditions start to show signs of decline according to scientific surveys, but not according to fishers own observations

- Experiment with new models of long-term fisher/science cooperation based on the model of ‘nøglefisker/nøgleflåde’ - pay special attention to building mutual trust, commitment and reliability in the process
- Consider joint research applications with APNIPN for development and capacity building in East Greenlandic fisheries

Marine governance gaps:

- Include East Greenlandic representative in the working group of the Fishery Council
- Consider if the special situation of new coastal fisheries in East Greenland provides a special opportunity to test co-management principles
- Provide more flexible regulations for Atlantic cod management in East Greenland: seasons and areas
- Increase monitoring and awareness of human economic activities in the National Park in East Greenland
- Facilitate close and continued contact between researchers, stakeholders and managers in order for all to have the most updated knowledge on changes and trends
- Consider new protection measures for seals (ringed seal) in the context of ice fiords ‘opening up’ and thereby increasing hunters’ access. Suggestions discussed (without final agreement) in the workshop included 1) consider a limit on how far into fiords hunting should be allowed 2) limit the hunting on breeding adults/large seals
- Clarification of the understanding and expectations towards ‘local knowledge’ - what is meant by the concept, and how can it be used in management?

Adaptation and development of the fishery:

- New boats and equipment can help fishers adapt to new fishing and hunting opportunities
- Knowledge exchange with Faroese islands could help hunters adapt to new opportunities of small whale hunting (pilot whales)
- Knowledge exchange and/or teaching by West-Greenlandic fishers can help develop the fisheries
- Explore and consider the role of carbon footprint in Greenlandic fisheries - as an argument for fishing and landing Greenlandic fish quota in Greenland, by Greenlandic fleets
- Consider possibilities for offshore trawlers to employ fishers from East Greenland